

I'm in higher education's third space: who is here with me?

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At the time of the Third Space Symposium (3SS), the third space was a concept I regularly encountered in articles, calls, and at conferences. I increasingly believed I was in the third space and wanted to understand who was there with me. By exploring who else was in the third space we would better understand current perspectives of higher education, the roles and relationships of those who consider themselves third space practitioners, how we all contribute to greater understanding and knowledge of the third space, and how we can ensure that we recognise and support one another.

As an academic leader in middle-senior management, when I first came across the concept I thought I was exempt, that the third space was not an area that academics or leaders could be part of, but I increasingly realised that this isn't so. Positioning this provocation for the 3SS, I posed a series of questions, inviting feedback via the 3SS forum; those questions included:

- Who is here in higher education's third space?
- How did you enter the third space?
- What makes you feel part of the third space?
- If you previously felt exempt, what led you to recognising your place in the third space?
- Have you always been part of the third space?
- How do we welcome fellow third space inhabitants?
- Other reflections, thoughts, and comments.

The aim of this provocation was to spark discussion, ignite ideas, and collate responses.

Reflections

The topic sparked interest and engagement, leading to being short-listed for the “best fora” during the 3SS. Delegates were very open in the experiences they shared, details of the roles they undertake and how they found themselves in the third space. The idea of questioning academic leadership positioning within the third space drew interest, with reflections from others around whether they previously would have considered such roles exempt, as I had. There was a general sense of the need for greater recognition and celebration of the activity happening within the third space, and a desire for more formal recognition of this work.

Further work

Prior to the 3SS, I received ethical approval from my institution to undertake research extending explorations into this topic. Delegates at the 3SS and another event, an online conference in the

autumn of 2024, were informed of this additional research and invited to participate in a separate questionnaire. The findings from this questionnaire have been analysed and submitted as a case study to a journal: the article is currently under final review and due for publication in the summer of 2026.

References

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